

CULTURAL ARTIFACTS AS EMOTIONAL CATALYSTS AND SOCIAL MEDIATORS IN DESIGN RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a reflection on the inclusion of Cultural Artifacts in the enhancement of design research methods, particularly probes. A Cultural Artifact is defined as an artifact, -- tangible or not -- that has imbedded meaning for a socio-cultural group and therefore has potential to elicit emotions in individuals. Ludic by nature, Cultural Artifacts are designed to be creative and inspirational. They consist in the appropriation of artifacts relevant to a group or culture and their deconstruction by a designer with the intention of discovering information traditionally overlooked by other research methods. One of the principal reasons for the inclusion of Cultural Artifacts is their potential to unveil thoughts, ideas, feelings and emotions that would otherwise be complicated for participants to express, explore and elicit.

Focus is placed on the artifacts' significance as emotional catalysts as well as their roles as social mediators between participants and researchers. Cultural Probes, a design research method typically consisting of a collection of self-documentation techniques and instruments serve as initial basis which we extend for cultural significance. Cultural Probes created initially by Gaver and Dunne of the Royal College of Art, were developed with the intention of eliciting emotional responses from participants.

This proposal of Cultural Artifacts is based on the first author's doctoral research in progress, zooming in on a Cultural Artifact developed for Mexican-American communities in Chicago, as well as the authors'

experience teaching Cultural Probes to graduate design students, researchers and participants in the United States, Mexico and Argentina.

Keywords: cultural artifact, design research method, user centered design.

INTRODUCTION

This paper illustrates the inclusion of Cultural Artifacts to extend the design research method known as Cultural Probes or Probes. A Cultural Artifact is defined as an artifact, -- tangible or not -- that has imbedded meaning for a socio-cultural group and therefore has potential to elicit emotions in individuals. "As fragments of the physical world, objects are often imbued with special significance because they span the divide between the inexpressible inner reality that each individual builds up from instinct, intuition and experience, and the outer world of forms" (Fontana, 1994, p68). One of the main reasons for the use of Cultural Artifacts in probes is their relevance as catalysts between the participant and his or her thoughts, ideas, feelings and emotions. The inclusion of Cultural Artifacts can also help to establish bonds between participants and design researchers by enhancing mutuality of understanding. Cultural Artifacts act as social mediators opening new spaces for dialogue between participants and researchers.

A probe can be defined as a collection of self-documentation techniques and instruments, typically consisting of journals, digital cameras, postcards, and engaging activities composed with the objective

of having participants record their thoughts and feelings while at the same time engaging them in the project. “The objective of probing then is about orienting towards users’ context and getting an understanding of the subjective elements of the context such as emotions, lifestyle, motivations and values” (Mattelmäki *et al.*, 2010, p2). Developed with the intention of eliciting emotional responses from users and fostering empathic relations between users and designers, probes are particularly useful for knowing and understanding users in their cultural context.

PROBE METHODOLOGY

While William Gaver and Tony Dunne of the Royal College of Art in London are credited with the introduction of Cultural Probes, other researchers have adapted and built upon probe methodology. Finnish researcher Tuuli Mattelmäki approaches probe methodology in a fashion similar to Gaver however she replaces the word “cultural” with “design”. Probes in Mattelmäki’s words are “meant to support both the designers and the users in their interpretations and creativity” (Mattelmäki, 2006, p40). Coming from a co-design tradition, Mattelmäki’s approach values the role of participants both in the creative and interpretive stages of the method. The researchers establish the difference between cultural and design probes in that in the former, participants’ self-documented information is left for the interpretation of the researchers. “The designers did not want the participants to explain their own interpretations of the material, specifically avoiding it, building their planning on their own views as well as the issues and insights emerging from the user material and the inspiration created by the material and the process” (Mattelmäki, 2006, p43).

Other researchers have also applied probe methods at later stages of the design process, such as idea generation and concept evaluation. Sharon Baurley, claims that when probing users she is “interested in using design methods to mobilize tacit knowledge from people about their aspirations, desires, experiences for the purposes of ideation and evaluation of concepts. Methods include generative

storyboarding, low-fi mockups, and prototypes that help gain insight into the catalysts and drivers of new products, and potential emergent consumer behaviour” (Baurley, accessed May 10, 2011).

For the research interests of the doctoral research in-progress reported herein, the approach considered is that proposed by researchers such as Gaver and Mattelmäki, where the information generated is intended to know, empathize and establish relationships with participants. The exploratory quality of the method lies in an effort to trigger emotions that is prioritized towards possible solutions to design problems. Mattelmäki explains that: “Probes have an exploratory character. They explore new opportunities rather than solve problems that are known already” (Mattelmäki, 2006, p40). Gaver *et al.* describe their approach that “[p]robes are collections of evocative tasks meant to elicit inspirational responses from people –not comprehensive information about them, but fragmentary clues about their lives and thoughts” (Gaver *et al.*, 2004, p1). Furthermore, “[t]he probes give us a deep sense of familiarity and engagement with the people who might use our designs, and this nourishes our design process at every stage” (Gaver *et al.*, 2004, p6).

One of the tenets of the argument for the inclusion of Cultural Artifacts in probes is that the connotation of the concept cultural is not circumscribed only to nationality or ethnicity. The context, behaviors, traditions and practices of everyday life of a socio-cultural group of individuals will be defined as the group’s culture. “As an intervention into scholarly production, cultural studies is above all concerned with the creation of new kinds of spaces for consideration of questions which do not fit neatly within established traditions of intellectual exchange” (Franklin, 2006, p135). Cultural Artifacts are located within the concept of *cultural capital*, one of the forms of capital proposed by philosopher Pierre Bourdieu. This concept “refers to cultural resources whose possession advantages agents. Bourdieu suggests that cultural capital may assume one of three forms:

--Objectified form: books, paintings, CDs, other objects and artifacts that an individual may own;
 --Institutionalized form: educational qualifications in particular;
 --Embodied form: valued competences (the capacity to talk meaningfully about art for example, speaking with posh accent)” (Crossley, 2005, p29).

CULTURAL ARTIFACTS

One cannot deny the relationship between humans and artifacts. Extending beyond the obvious relationship of men -- and women -- being the creators, artifacts have been active participants of society’s advancement, if not necessarily progress. Their relevance is such that historically, artifacts -- either tangible or intangible -- have been point of reference to divide different eras of humanity. A stone arrow, the wheel, the locomotive, the light bulb and software suggest only examples of the roles they play in our lives. On a micro level, our daily life would be difficult if not inconvenient if it were not for the presence of artifacts around us. Some are necessary, some are practical, some are cherished. Some are all of the above.

Caplan makes this point in reference to Tim O’Brien’s book *The Things They Carried* which takes its title from a story that relates “the objects carried by soldiers in Vietnam to the emotions and experiences they signified. Lieutenant Cross carried his good luck pebble. Dave Jensen carried a rabbit’s foot... They carried Sterno, safety pins... spools of wire, razor blades, chewing tobacco, liberated joss sticks and statuettes of the smiling Buddha. ...They carried all they could bear, and then some, including silent awe for the terrible power of the things they carried” (Caplan, 2005, p52). And then those simple objects the soldiers carried acted also as a connection to their loved ones back in the United States. The Vietnam Memorial in Washington D.C., a granite wall with more than 58,000 names of the war casualties etched on it, is a dynamic monument in the sense that it is transformed daily by the objects left at its base. “These objects, left mostly by families and friends of those lost in combat are cultural objects. Even though they may seem common, they have been carefully selected because

of their meaning to the soldiers. Examples of objects left include letters, cans of beer, the exact amount of coins necessary to make a phone call home and a wedding band” (Ornelas, 2002, p26). Hass describes how “[a]t the Wall, the objects become unique and irreplaceable. They are meant to be shared and act as participants in the memories of others” (Hass, 1998, p26).

TEACHING CULTURAL ARTIFACTS

The first Cultural Artifacts course in the Master of Design program at the Institute of Design, Illinois Institute of Technology in Chicago (hereafter IIT Institute of Design) was taught in Spring 2011 under the name “Cultural Probes.” In the first assignment, the students were asked to select an object, concept and/or metaphor unique to their culture and present it to the rest of the class during the next session, explaining its history, meaning, relevance, use and significance. Although a seemingly easy assignment, the instruction underlined notions that made students reflect on their own self awareness as individuals within a culture. In order to present their Cultural Artifacts in the class, each student first had to come to terms with the notion of culture.

Complicated as culture is, the challenge was even greater when we consider that the majority of these students live in one culture but were brought up and nurtured in a different one. For those who consider themselves as being part of one culture -- many the students who identify as ‘Americans’ -- the task was not easier in any way. Being “in” their own culture, it was hard for them to look introspectively first and then look for an artifact unique to their culture.

The diversity of Cultural Artifacts presented by students at the Cultural Probes course is an example of how relationships are forged between objects and people. The majority of artifacts presented fell into the “chronologically passed-down” category of objects handed from one generation to the next. A student whose family roots are from Russia selected caviar as her Cultural Artifact. She not only described the meaning and connotations caviar has for Russian culture, but also explained the preconceived misconceptions about caviar outside of

Russia. She explained that even though caviar is not cheap in Russia it is not seen as a luxury item. An intrinsic ingredient of family and friends gatherings, caviar is also the traditional dish for excellence when entertaining guests. The packaging of caviar in shallow tin cans with bold colors also plays an important role for triggering memories about the meaning of this culturally specific artifact.

On the other hand, other students presented artifacts that are intangible concepts powerful enough in their significance in the everyday life of the group to be considered as Cultural Artifacts. For example, one student discussed the manicured lawn as a Cultural Artifact of American culture. What could be considered to be a highly abstract artifact was grounded firmly by the student explaining what manicured lawns represent for American families. Lawns are the first sight you have of houses, the most intimate of all spaces. People invest energy in such lawns. It is almost as if the family and neighborhood values are reflected in manicured lawns. Going through family photo albums looking for a picture to show to the class, the student realized that all pictures of gatherings happening in the house, either casual or formal, had people standing on the grass. As Csikszentmihalyi writes of domestic symbols and the self:

“Among humans, adaptive strategies are particularly flexible, because they are shaped not primarily by genetic and environmental determining conditions but by symbolic forces whose purposes almost always extend beyond mere adaptation. The extent to which the physical environment is elaborated with communicative signs that reveal the specific characteristics of the inhabitants is, with language, one of the distinguishing features of human life. Although we live in physical environments, we create cultural environments within them” (Csikszentmihalyi, 1999, p122).

The meanings of the space, conceptually and somewhat subconsciously delimited by its users, transforms the lawn into a Cultural Artifact. Cultural Artifacts have the power to make visible the

immaterial from the material form. Having a shared, symbolic meaning, understanding Cultural Artifacts underlines the notion of belonging to a socio-cultural group. “Since the history of the individual is never anything other than a certain specification of the collective history of his group or class, each individual system of dispositions may be seen as a structural variant of all the other group or class habitus, expressing the difference between trajectories and positions inside or outside the class” (Bourdieu, 1977, p86).

Cultural Artifacts embody the collective memories -- both real and imagined -- of a group in society. “Memory is never shaped in a vacuum, the motives of memory are never pure. Every generation constructs memorials to inculcate its own priorities in succeeding generations” (Young, 1993, p56). They also act as markers of memory. The texture of memory imbedded in artifacts is usually passed down chronologically, that is through generations, although some artifacts are appropriated when a person becomes part of a group.

In 2009, a Cultural Artifact inspired by the Mexican game called *Lotería* was developed by the first author to understand everyday life experiences especially related to health and well-being -- *bienestar* -- of Mexican-American families in Chicago (Figure 1). The artifact was one method in a variety of research methods employed in the project *Bienestar/Wellness Experience Research* that took a sharp focus on diabetes in Chicago’s Latino communities (2009-2010), as part of an initiative for ‘Rethinking Health’ with design thinking of the IIT Institute of Design led by the second author (2007-2010). The intention behind the selection of the *Lotería* game as the artifact basis for the probe was to evoke the participants’ memories and emotions in order for the design researchers to get to know individuals in the community on a more personal level. For this connection to happen, there was a need to rely on an artifact that is both socially and culturally inclusive.

Lotería is a popular game of chance in Mexico, sometimes referred to as “Mexican Bingo”. Played by

people of all ages, it consists of 52 cards and 8 individual game-boards. The game features both universal images and symbols related to Mexican culture, history and traditions. Ranging from common, universal images -- such as the sun, a rose, a fish, and mythological creatures such as a mermaid and the devil -- to metaphors closely related to Mexican culture such as the *chalupa* (a woman selling flowers on a canoe) and *calaca* (festive death), the cards represent and encompass Mexicans' hopes, values, fears, and desires.

For this project, the *lotería* game was deconstructed in the sense that the materials were not used in the way the game is played. Only the 52 playing cards (each with a different image) were selected for the design of the *Lotería* as a Cultural Artifact method in a workshop and in a probe kit. Nine questions were provided to participants, each printed on a blank card the same size as the *Lotería* cards. Each blank card had a metal ring attached to it. The questions asked were aspirational and metaphorical, for example: *If you could give yourself a gift that would change your life, what would it be?* And *If you could be one (or several) Lotería cards, which one(s)*

would you like to be, and why? Besides the nine questions and the 52 *Lotería* cards, there was a small card with the instructions to answer with the probe (Figure 2). Participants were asked to answer the nine questions in a written form and then select and attach to the ring the image(s) that they thought would relate to each question. The cards were used to trigger deeper emotional responses based on nostalgic association of recognizable images. Participants had the option to give textual or visual answers, or both.

Approximately twelve people participated in this stage of the *Bienestar/Wellness Experience* project. Probes including the *Lotería* Cultural Artifact plus other self-documentation materials were delivered to participants. Family members took the probe kit home for a week. Once the design team received the answered probes, information was analyzed and follow-up contextual interviews were conducted with participants in their homes. The *Lotería* Cultural Artifact was a success in that it made it possible to establish an immediate connection between participants and the design researchers. The design team observed that when the probe kit was

Figure 1. Cultural Artifact using the *Lotería* cards as nostalgic inspiration. *Bienestar/Wellnes Experience* project, 2009-2010.

delivered and the materials were explained to community participants, a sense of emotion and curiosity showed in their facial expressions when they discovered the *Lotería* cards. Participants did not question the atypical use of the cards; they were intrigued by the activity with a sense of inclusion and respect on the part of the design team.

Even though the *Lotería* was deconstructed and decontextualized participants did not have a problem doing the activity. All of the questions were answered, some only in written form, some only with images and some responses with textual and visual answers (Figure 3). One of the most interesting outcomes of the activity pragmatics, was the fact that in some of the cases, the images chosen as answers were not directly related to the written answer. In other words images were an alternate answer to text.

The answered probe kits were returned to the design team for analysis. Of the activities included, it was the *Lotería* Cultural Artifact that provided the most emotional and culturally significant answers. Some of the responses were frankly intriguing and abstract

for the researchers to interpret, especially those that were answered only using *Lotería* images. Follow-up interviews with participants gave the opportunity to researchers to talk discuss the responses further with the participants. Altogether, this was a great way to establish a more empathic connection between design researchers and participants. Although the written answers were very valuable, it was important to ask about the images they selected. Usually their explanations were more complex (thus harder to write down) and had the potential to offer the research team more interesting insights.

CONCLUSION

The respect and sensibility infused in probes with Cultural Artifacts can enable researchers to establish a deeper connection with participants. Establishing such strong and mutual relationships proves fruitful for rapport throughout all stages of the design process. The argument for including Cultural Artifacts in probes is to augment photo studies and journals (traditional ethnographic methods typically included in probes). For probes to be more effective and culturally inclusive, the artifacts selected for

Figure 2. The *Lotería* Cultural Artifact delivered to participants consisted of a set of 52 *lotería* cards, 9 questions, an instruction card, and a marker in a transparent pouch.

designing a probe need to be familiar and simple enough to participants, yet powerful enough to elicit complex responses.

The relevance of culturally inclusive research methods cannot be understated in our multicultural world. The ideation, production and launching of Cultural Artifacts requires an understanding and/or appreciation of participants' culture (customs, behaviors, traditions, thoughts, ways of living). The design and deployment of a Cultural Artifact is particularly useful when designers are seeking to understand a foreign group or different culture. Probes and Cultural Artifacts are also advised when seeking to gain understandings about users whose location is remote and/or when access is otherwise difficult.

Interpretation of the materials and information generated from Cultural Artifacts probes is subjective; however, the power of this method resides in the inspiration that the knowledge obtained brings to the design researchers' table. Understanding users from uniquely individual

perspectives within their cultural context, taking into consideration individuals' similarities and differences, abets the success of an inclusive and sensible design solution tailored to the participants' necessities. In researching the semiotic constituents and abstractness of mediating artifacts in design, Hahn presents a description of their advantages, highlighting their descriptive, evocative, simulating, representational and engaging qualities (Hahn, 2009, p80).

Although some traditional ethnographic methods and techniques are typically included in a Probe, a distinguishing sensibility of the inclusion of a Cultural Artifact to Probe methods is that the probe -- taken as a whole comprising artifactual elements, activities, assignments and expressive means provided to a participant -- has a personal touch, and in that regard, a more inclusive quality than standard research methods. Cultural Artifacts bring users back to the center of more deeply user-centered design, by educating design researchers to create probes in a reflexive, sensible and inclusive manner. Standardizing design research methods in a

Figure 3. Examples of answered Loteria Cultural Artifact. Some questions were answered with text and images, some had only textual answers and some others had only visual answers.

multicultural context will inevitably cause sensible information to get lost in the generalization of such methods.

Probes are meant to be creative, poetic, provocative and inspirational. They open new spaces for doing research through design. Through analysis of qualitative data and findings from probes, researchers are presented with opportunities to find inspirations, explore emotions, and wander through the boundaries of cultures. Whether we are talking about a board game, a tin can of caviar or manicured front yards, it is clear that the inclusion of artifacts embedded with meanings that extend beyond their originally intended function provides designers with an opportunity to tap into the depths of emotional resonances for individuals. This will not only result into a more empathic relationship between designers and participants, it will also produce richer information that would otherwise be kept hidden inside the participants' minds and hearts. "That part of practices which remains obscure in the eyes of their own producers is the aspect by which they are objectively adjusted to other practices and to the structures of which the principle of their production is itself the product" (Bourdieu, 1977, p86).

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